

Paper 4

**QUALITY EDUCATION: EDUCATIONAL INNOVATION OF
TEACHERS AND STUDENTS BY USE OF DIGITAL MEDIA**

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ABSTRACT

Quality, now a days has high relevance and importance in every field be it product, service, process etc. In education industry, teachers have a major role in providing quality education. The process of quality is cyclic where the continuous development of teachers improves the teaching quality, removing the deficiencies, and in turn bringing in excellence in resources, reputation, content and outcome. The outcome being the overall development of the students like the social, emotional, mental, physical, and cognitive development. In the context of westernisation, modernisation and professionalization of education system, parents, management and everyone want their children to be taught by competent, qualified and professional teachers. Effective teaching is a key responsibility of each and every teacher. It is based on teacher’s teaching experience and their performance too. Teachers play a dynamic role in the educational system. Good performance of students depends upon effective teaching of their teachers. Teachers should focus on quality improvement to impart quality education for the overall development of their students and not to measure quality in terms of students’ academic achievement. Academic achievement is not a competent measure of educational quality since it depends on many other factors such as student’s innate intelligence, study habits, learning styles, motivation, parental socio-economic status and home environment. Hence, we have to identify relevant indicators of educational quality and measure it in a reliable and valid manner.

Key words: Quality education, Professionalization of educational system, teacher’s quality, teaching quality, dimensions of education, learning outcomes, student centred and a lifelong learning.

INTRODUCTION

Quality, now a days has high relevance and importance in every field be it product, service, process etc. In education industry, teachers have a major role in providing quality education. The

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process of quality is cyclic where the continuous development of teachers improves the teaching quality, removing the deficiencies, and in turn bringing in excellence in resources, reputation, content and outcome. The outcome being the overall development of the students like the social, emotional, mental, physical, and cognitive development.

MEANING OF QUALITY EDUCATION:

Quality education enables students to develop all of their attributes and skills to achieve their potentiality as human beings and members of society.

TEACHER’S FOR QUALITY AND REFORMS TO IMPROVE TEACHERS EFFICIENCY:

The primary role of teacher is to deliver the classroom instruction that helps the students to learn effectively. Teacher’s quality is said to be the most important factor influencing learning outcomes. The teacher carefully evaluates how to achieve learning goals, choosing alternative teaching strategies and materials to achieve different instructional purposes and to meet student needs.

“Tell me and I forget, teach me and I may remember, involve me and I Learn.” As quoted by Benjamin Franklin, on his opinion on educational reforms.

QUALITY EDUCATION AND REFORMS TO IMPROVE TEACHER’S EFFICIENCY:

The focus of educational reforms and innovations should be on teaching and learning theory and practice as well as on the learner, parents, community, society and its culture. A Quality education is one that focuses on the whole child/ student- the social, emotional, mental, physical, and cognitive development of each student regardless of gender, race, ethnicity, socio-economic status or geographic location. It prepares the child for life not just for testing.

ROLE OF TEACHERS IN QUALITY EDUCATION:

In the context of westernisation, modernisation and professionalisation of education system, parents, management and everyone want their children to be taught by competent, qualified and professional teachers.

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There are different crucial dimensions of quality education like:

1. Continuous improvement
2. Contextualisation
3. Relevance
4. Child friendly teaching and learning
5. Sustainability
6. Balanced approach
7. Learning outcomes
8. Career guidance and job opportunities
9. Overall development

Effective teaching is a key responsibility of each and every teacher. It is based on teacher's teaching experience and their performance too. Teachers play a dynamic role in the educational system. Good performance of students depends upon effective teaching of their teachers.

At the same time, education system must ensure inclusive and quality education for promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all. Everyone is not born the same and are not equal. Likewise, the students are different in thinking and are unique in their own way. Role of teachers in Quality Education is their ability to evolve themselves to be effective teachers and at the same time, understand and identify the skills, qualities in their students and strive towards their upliftment. It includes getting everyone to the mainstream of education through improved performance, overall development and thus making the younger generation well equipped to face the world. Nelson Mandela rightly said, “Education is the most powerful weapon which you can use to change the World.”

Teacher's quality refers to the characteristics that teachers possess. Teacher's quality includes teacher professional preparation characteristics and teacher knowledge and their ability to guide students to achieve wholesome development as an individual.

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online training and its implementation in the field.

- The purpose of this study is to analyze the satisfaction level of educational innovation perceived and experienced between teachers and students, regarding innovation and quality of education through online classes

DESIGN OF THE STUDY/METHODOLOGY/APPROACH:

- The study is based on the online survey.

FEEDBACK

PERCENTAGE

COLLECT

RESPONDENTS	NUMBER	SATISFIED	%	REMARKS
TEACHERS	16	VERY MUCH	32%	HEALTH, TIME, COST INVOLVED
STUDENTS-PROFESSIONAL	12	VERY MUCH	24%	EFFECTIVE
STUDENTS-GENERAL	12	ATTENDED, BUT NOT SO SATISFIED	24%	DOUBTS CANT BE SOLVED
OTHERS	10	CANT SAY	20%	NO INFORMATION
TOTAL	50		100%	

Feedback summary

Findings:

- The results of the study show that satisfaction of educational innovation perceived and experienced differently between teachers and students, regarding innovation and quality of

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education through online classes.

- 32% Of the Teachers found it relevant with the conduct of online classes
- 24% of the Professional students found relevancy with the conduct of online classes
- 24% of the respondents not satisfied with the conduct of online classes
- 20% of the respondents proper data not available

DRAWBACKS

- Health of the Teachers and students
- Internet Issues
- Teachers cannot communicate properly and solving students becomes difficult

Conclusion:

- The primary focus of educational innovations should be on teaching and learning theory and practice, as well as on the learner, parents, community, society, and its culture.
- Technology applications need a solid theoretical foundation based on purposeful, systemic research, and a sound pedagogy.
- One of the critical areas of research and innovation can be cost and time efficiency of the learning and health issues in online learning.
- Effect of technology innovations in education. There is transformation of teaching practices.

Learning to skills and life

“If you want to live a happy life, Tie it to a Goal, Not to People or Things”
